

Results of quality tests of particle boards from rice straw.

Raw materials	Density (kg/m ³)	Modulus of rupture ^a (kg/cm ²)
1 Rice straw + resin + hardener (5% by wt)	331	135
2 Rice straw + resin + hardener (10% by wt)	680	325
3 Rice straw + resin + hardener (15% by wt)	780	360
4 Rice straw + resin + hardener (20% by wt)	950	389
5 Boards from coconut husk ^b	1310	254
6 Boards from wood dust ^b	890	324
Requirements of IS-3129/1965	< 400	15
Requirements of IS-3087/1965	500-900	90
Requirements of IS-3478/1966	> 900	225

^aModulus of rupture was assessed for 1-cm-thick boards. ^bSource: Indian Plywood Industries Research Institute, Bangalore 22.

temperature), glazed boards, chop boards, and blockboards. Boards with a density of up to 950 kg/m³ were made

by altering the resin type, resin:straw ratio, and pressure while drying. It was possible to produce glazed boards by

using resin abundantly on the surface. Veneer boards can also be manufactured by pressing a resin and straw mixture between two layers of thin wooden boards.

Rice straw boards have low density and are lightweight when compared with boards from wood dust and coconut husk, yet attain higher modulus of rupture (Table 1).

Production costs can be substantially reduced using rice straw as the raw material compared with other materials. Total cost in \$/m² of a 1-cm-thick board is \$2.53 for rice straw, \$3.68 for coconut husk, and \$3.14 for wood dust. □

Evaluation of suitable rice and pigeonpea varieties for intercropping under upland conditions in Orissa, India

D. Chandra, Agronomy Division, Central Rice Research Institute (CRRRI), Cuttack 753006. Orissa; A. R. Raju, Central Institute for Cotton Research, Nagpur, Maharashtra; and U. D. Singh, Plant Pathology Division, CRRRI, India

We initiated a trial during 1990 wet season to determine suitable rice and pigeonpea varieties for intercropping under upland conditions in Cuttack. We intercropped rice varieties Annada (105 d duration) and Safed Heera (75 d) with pigeonpea varieties ICPL 85010 (120 d), Bahar (280 d), and T-7 (287 d). We used the recommended fertilizer level of 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha for rice and 20-26-25 kg NPK/ha for pigeonpea. All of the P and K and half of the N were applied in the furrows at seeding. The remaining N was topdressed in sole crops but placed in furrows and mixed into the soil in intercrops.

Based on recommendations of the International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics, Hyderabad, short-duration ICPL 85010 was planted in a 1:1 ratio of rice-pigeonpea and long-duration pigeonpea varieties Bahar and T-7 were used in a 3:1 rice-pigeonpea ratio; all were sown on 11 Jun 1990.

The 11 treatment combinations were randomly allocated in a randomized

Grain yield, land-equivalent ratio, and net monetary returns under different rice + pigeonpea intercropping systems.

Rice + pigeonpea system	Mean grain yield (t/ha)		Land-equivalent ratio	Net monetary returns (\$/ha)
	Main crop	Intercrop		
Safed Heera + ICPL 85010	1.6	0.3	1.56	57.79
Safed Heera + Bahar	1.6	0.8	1.74	194.88
Safed Heera + T-7	1.8	0.6	1.74	157.33
Annada + ICPL 85010	2.2	0.3	1.69	110.93
Annada + Bahar	1.9	0.8	1.64	206.81
Annada + T-7	2.4	0.8	1.88	251.55
Safed Heera alone	1.9	—	1.00	49.13
Annada alone	2.4	—	1.00	86.51
ICPL 85010 alone	0.4	—	1.00	68.53
Bahar alone	0.9	—	1.00	194.84
T-7 alone	0.9	—	1.00	193.86

block design with three replications. The soil of the experimental field is sandy loam alluvial (Inceptisol).

Yield data indicated that Annada (CR222, MW10) intercropped with T-7 produced the highest yields, showed the greatest land-equivalent ratio, and had the maximum net monetary return of \$251.55/ha. It gave an extra net benefit of \$57.70/ha compared with growing T-7 alone. Intercropping rice with the other pigeonpea varieties neither produced higher yields nor extra

monetary returns (see table).

The Safed Heera rice crop had more weeds when it was intercropped with pigeonpea. More than 60% of the Safed Heera crop suffered from sheath blight (ShB) when intercropped with pigeonpea ICPL 85010 in a 1:1 ratio. This increased ShB incidence may be due to increased humidity inside the crop canopies.

Intercropping Annada and T-7 under the studied agroclimatic conditions can be beneficial. □

Space limitations prevent IRRN from publishing solely yield and yield component data from fertilizer field trials that are not conducted for at least two cropping seasons or at two differing sites. Publication of work in a single season or at one site is limited to manuscripts that provide either a) data and analysis beyond yield and yield components (e.g., floodwater parameters, microbial populations, soil mineral N dynamics, organic acid concentrations, or mineralization rates for organic N sources), or b) novel ways of interpreting yield and yield component data across seasons and sites.